

Clinical and Pathological Design of Breast Cancer Presentation in Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore.

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Abstract:

Objective: The main aim of this study was to find the presentations of breast cancer on the basis of clinical and pathological features.

Place and duration of study: This study was carried out in a duration of 9 months from February 2018 to October 2018 in Sir Ganga Ram hospital Lahore.

Materials and Methods: A total of 500 patients with breast cancer were selected for the study in which either surgery had been performed or who were referred for the radiotherapy or chemotherapy. All the relevant investigations were done and staging was done using triple assessment. ER, PR HER2 Neu receptors were also assessed. Informed consent was taken from all the patients or their relatives. Ethical committee approval was taken. Data was collected using pre-designed questionnaire.

Results: A total of 500 patients were selected in which the mean age ranged between 25 to 80 years. Highest incidence of breast cancer was seen in the patients between the age group of 40 to 50 years (57%). Stage III and IV advanced tumors were seen in 64% of the patients. Most common type seen was invasive ductal carcinoma 93%. On histopathology grade II tumor was seen in majority of the patients about 55%.

Conclusion: Our study shows that during 40 to 50 years of age, highest incidence of breast cancer is seen and invasive ductal carcinoma is the commonest type and cases with advance stage disease are more common.

Keywords: Breast carcinoma, prevalence, invasive ductal carcinoma.

Introduction: Most common carcinoma seen in women all over the world is breast cancer. 45% of women in Pakistan are affected by breast cancer making it most common malignancy even in Pakistan. Around one out of every nine females in Pakistan suffers from breast cancer. In Pakistan, unawareness about the disease leads to delayed presentations and with advance stage of III or IV. High grade invasive ductal carcinoma is the most common type that affects young and middle aged patients. Biological markers like estrogen and

progesterone receptors are mostly evaluated in breast cancer patients. Positive HER2 Neu receptors along with negative ER and PR receptors in a patient is associated with poor prognosis.

Materials and Methods: A total of 500 patients with breast cancer were selected for the study in which either surgery had been performed or who were referred for the radiotherapy or chemotherapy. All the relevant investigations were done and staging was done using triple assessment. ER, PR HER2 Neu receptors were also assessed. Informed consent was taken from all the patients or their relatives. Ethical committee approval was taken. Data was collected using pre-designed questionnaire.

Results: 500 patients with ages between 25 to 80 years were included in this study. In age group 40 to 50 years, there were 285 (57%) patients. Above the age of 50 years there were 100 (20%) females. In age group of 30 to 40 years, there were 75 (15%) females.

On the basis of staging, stage I patients were 80 (16%) according to UICC. In stage II there were 100 (20%) patients, stage III included 250 (50%) patients and in stage IV there were 70 (14%) patients.

Invasive ductal carcinoma was seen in 65 (93%) of the cases on the basis of histopathology, invasive lobular carcinoma was seen in 20 (4%) of the cases, mixed ductal and lobular carcinoma was seen in 2% while metastatic carcinoma was found in 5 (1%) of the cases.

Different percentages were seen in different grades of tumor. Grade II tumor was seen in 275 (55%) cases, grade III in 210 (42%) while grade I was seen only in 15 (3%) of the cases.

250 (65.8%) patients were progesterone and estrogen positive while 130 (34.2%) were negative for PR and ER. 75 (15%) patients were having ER, PR, HER-2Neu positive studies and 55 patients

(11%) with HER-2Neu positive status were ER, PR negative.

Discussion: This study was carried out to look for the presentations of breast cancer on the basis of clinical and pathological features.

Highest incidence of breast cancer was seen in the patients between the age group of 40 to 50 years (57%). Similar results were shown by Wani et al in which 46 ± 10.2 years was the mean age. Mean age in a study done by Naeem et al was 40 to 49 years while it was 41 to 50 years in a study conducted by Baloch A H et al.

Most common type seen was invasive ductal carcinoma 93%. Our findings are comparable to other studies done in Pakistan which shows incidence of invasive ductal carcinoma to be 95.5% in Baluchistan and 92% in Lahore in a study done in INMOL hospital Lahore.

Khokhar s et al in his study showed that most common presentation is advanced type of breast cancer which coincides with our study in which 64% of the patients were seen in stage III and IV.

Our study shows that during 40 to 50 years of age, highest incidence of breast cancer is seen and invasive ductal carcinoma is the commonest type and cases with advance stage disease are more common.

High incidence seen in Pakistan is because of the lack of awareness about the disease and poor screening facilities in women.

Conclusion: Our study shows that during 40 to 50 years of age, highest incidence of breast cancer is seen and invasive ductal carcinoma is the commonest type and cases with advance stage disease are more common.

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